

REGULATORY AND LEGAL SUPPORT FOR THE STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF CYBERCRIME RISKS IN UZBEKISTAN

Khasanov Umidjon Yusupovich

Bukhara State University

independent researcher

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The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Cybersecurity” [2] may be cited as the main legal document regulating the cybersecurity sector in the country

ABSTRACT

The analyses conducted show that, under the current conditions of the functioning of the public administration system in Uzbekistan, the legal foundations for the strategic management of cybercrime risks have been formed through a multi-level regulatory and legal framework. This framework includes constitutional norms, sectoral laws, criminal-law mechanisms, and presidential and government resolutions. In general, through a systematic analysis of the legal foundations related to the field of strategic management of cybercrime risks currently in force in the country, we identified the following systemically important problems that have not yet found practical solutions.

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the risk-oriented approach is not reflected at the same level in all regulatory legal documents;

the legal mechanisms of interdepartmental cooperation and information exchange require further strengthening;

there is a need to update legal norms for modern forms of cybercrime, including attacks using artificial intelligence, cryptocurrency-based fraud, and ransomware;

because the national cybersecurity strategy does not clearly define a strategic risk-management model, there are inconsistencies and contradictions among the current legal foundations related to the strategic management of cybercrime risks. In recent years, newly adopted regulatory legal documents have often tended to contradict one another, which creates the need to systematize the legal foundations according to a unified scheme.

At this point, we considered it necessary to focus the research on the functional features of the legal foundations related to the strategic management of cybercrime risks in the public

administration system of Uzbekistan. According to the analysis, the fundamental legal source for ensuring national security, human rights, and information security in the country is the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1]. This regulatory document is characterized by the fact that it establishes the inviolability of citizens' private life, the right to access information, and security guarantees provided by the state. At the same time, the fact that the current Constitution does not directly express the concept of strategic management of cybercrime risks has created the need to develop special legislation in this area.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Cybersecurity" [2] may be cited as the main legal document regulating the cybersecurity sector in the country. It was also determined that this law covers mechanisms related to the practice of strategic management of cybercrime risks in the country, including establishing mechanisms for preventing cyber incidents, introducing procedures for risk assessment in state information systems, legally strengthening the protection of critical information infrastructures, and defining the foundations of cooperation among state bodies in the field of cybersecurity. Along with the powers and obligations of state bodies, operators of critical information infrastructures, and other entities, this law establishes that cybersecurity in the country shall be ensured on the basis of the following principles:

"legality;

the priority of protecting the interests of the individual, society, and the state in cyberspace;

a unified approach to the regulation of the cybersecurity sector;

the priority of the participation of domestic producers in the creation of the cybersecurity system;

the openness of the Republic of Uzbekistan to international cooperation in ensuring cybersecurity" [2].

In addition, along with the above-mentioned positive aspects of applying this law in the practice of strategic management of cybercrime risks in the country, it can be observed that problems such as interdepartmental coordination, information exchange, and the lack of uniform technical standards have not yet been fully resolved in practical terms.

At present, in Uzbekistan, the legal support for the protection of citizens' personal data in state bodies is implemented through the Law "On Personal Data" [3]. This legal framework serves to reduce cybercrime risks in the public administration system by forming mechanisms to prevent the illegal dissemination, damage, or theft of data. In particular, measures in this area are organized on the basis of the following principles:

"respect for the constitutional rights and freedoms of individuals and citizens;

the legality of the purposes and methods of personal data processing;

the accuracy and reliability of personal data;

the confidentiality and protection of personal data;

the equality of the rights of subjects, owners, and operators;

the security of the individual, society, and the state" [3].

According to the analysis, the institutional foundations for the strategic management of cybercrime risks in the public administration system of Uzbekistan have been formed as a multi-level mechanism based on functional distribution. It is implemented through the

interaction of state institutions responsible for political governance, law enforcement, the development of digital infrastructure, and the provision of information security. The main purpose of this institutional system is to protect state information resources, digital services, and critical information infrastructures from cyber threats and to minimize risks associated with cybercrime.

References:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (new edition), May 1, 2023.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-764 "On Cybersecurity", April 15, 2022.
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-547 "On Personal Data", July 2, 2019.

